

THE AGING OF BULK ACOUSTIC WAVE RESONATORS,
FILTERS AND OSCILLATORS

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Abstract.

The aging of quartz crystal resonators, filters, and oscillators is reviewed, including the topics of: the impacts of aging, typical aging characteristics, aging specifications, aging mechanisms, temperature dependence of aging, frequency and overtone dependence of aging, drive level dependence of aging, the effects of aging interruptions, the dependence of aging on material and mode type, the state-of-the-art in low-aging oscillators, and aging acceleration effects. The aging mechanisms discussed include: contamination transfer effects, stress effects, electrode effects, diffusion effects, changes in the quartz material, and circuit and other electrical changes. Isothermal and thermal step stress aging acceleration methods are also reviewed.

Introduction.

The long term time dependence of a frequency source's frequency is often called frequency aging. Since other long term changes can occur, such as changes in the elements of the equivalent circuit of a crystal resonator, and in a crystal oscillator's input power ("input power aging" is defined in MIL-O-55310 [1]), clarity of expression requires that the particular parameter of interest be specifically stated. In the remainder of this paper, "aging" will mean frequency aging, unless otherwise specified.

"Aging" and "drift" have occasionally been used interchangeably in the frequency control literature. However, in 1990, recognizing the "need for common terminology for the unambiguous specification and description of frequency and time standard systems," the CCIR adopted a glossary of terms and definitions [2].

According to this glossary, aging is "the systematic change in frequency with time due to internal changes in the oscillator." Added to the definition is: "Note - It is the frequency change with time when factors external to the

oscillator (environment, power supply, etc.) are kept constant." Drift is defined as "the systematic change in frequency with time of an oscillator." Drift is due to aging plus changes in the environment and other factors external to the oscillator. Aging is what one specifies and what one measures during oscillator evaluation. Drift is what one observes in an application. For example, the drift of an oscillator in a spacecraft is due to (the algebraic sum of) aging and frequency changes due to radiation, temperature changes in the spacecraft, and power supply changes.

The CCIR definitions of aging and drift are now incorporated into the military specifications for crystal oscillators, MIL-O-55310 [1], and have been recommended by the IEEE Standards Coordinating Committee 27 on Time and Frequency for inclusion in the next edition of the IEEE Standard Dictionary of Electrical and Electronics Terms.

Random changes of frequency with time, called short term stability (or, more correctly, short term instability), are characterized in the time domain by the two-sample deviation (also called the square-root of the Allan variance), and in the frequency domain by the various measures of phase noise, as defined in IEEE Standard 1139-1988 [3].

The very accurate and precise measurement of frequency allows the observation of very small changes in a resonator. It is generally true that the crystal resonance frequency is a more sensitive measure of the state of the resonator system than other measurements that can be made. It has therefore been very difficult to apply measurements other than frequency to studies of the nature of the aging process, particularly for low-aging devices.

Many aging measurements have been reported, but few have included a detailed scientific or statistical study of the aging processes. Our understanding of resonator aging processes is often based on indirect evidence gained from

other fields (such as material science, and the science of solid surfaces), and on process developments that seemed "sensible" for general reasons, and which were followed by an evaluation of the resulting aging. For high aging rate resonators, advanced surface science measurements seem to support the use of the "sensible" processes by qualitatively correlating with the measured aging.

The "sensible" processes generally include suitable crystal surface preparation, high level of cleanliness during assembly of the resonator, reasonably well controlled crystal mounting and processing, and hermetically sealing the resonator into a clean enclosure. High temperature in-process baking is often used at some stage of resonator fabrication, such as after mounting, or before final frequency adjustment or sealing. Sometimes a burn-in after sealing is used to "preage" the resonator before shipment, and to test for processing deviations.

Precision crystal resonators need to be protected from operating system environments by sealing in an appropriate package. Typically, these packages have been glass or metal. For these glass or metal packaged resonators the resulting resonator system is very complex, in different ways. Mechanical, chemical, and electrical interactions between the package, the enclosed materials, and the resonator all can cause aging.

In a crystal oscillator, in addition to the aging of the resonator, aging of some of the electrical elements (for example, series inductance or load capacitance) can also change the oscillator's frequency. Changes in the shape and configuration of the metal leads, and deformation of circuit boards and enclosures can also produce aging.

Some of the aging of crystal filters is probably associated with the aging of associated electrical elements. Otherwise, crystal filters are subject to the same aging processes as other types of resonators.

The following sections of this paper contain discussions and references to published reports on the topics that are relevant to our understanding of the aging of resonators, crystal oscillators, and crystal filters. The emphasis is on reviewing aging processes, and the literature since 1983. The pre-1983 literature was reviewed by Gerber [4].

The Impacts of Aging.

In most device applications, the frequency of the oscillator must remain within specified limits in order for the device to operate properly. When aging shifts the frequency

beyond the limits, the oscillator must be recalibrated. Since crystal oscillators have a finite frequency adjustment range, oscillator aging can cause "end-of-life" when the aging rate is so high that it produces a frequency offset that exceeds the frequency adjustment range. (This rarely happens in properly designed oscillators.)

Soon after an oscillator's calibration, the frequency offset due to aging is usually small compared to the frequency offsets due to environmental (especially temperature) changes, however, eventually, the frequency offset due to aging becomes the dominant frequency offset. For example, a state-of-the-art oven controlled crystal oscillator is specified to have a frequency vs. temperature stability of 1×10^{-9} , an aging rate of 1×10^{-10} per day, and a frequency adjustment range of 4×10^{-7} . Assuming a worst-case linear aging rate at the specified rate, the frequency offset due to aging will equal the worst case temperature induced offset on the tenth day after calibration, and the oscillator will no longer be able to be calibrated after 4000 days (i.e., 11 years).

Similarly in clocks, aging eventually becomes the dominant time error source. Whereas the time error varies linearly with elapsed time due to the relatively constant clock rate errors (i.e., frequency offsets) caused by environmental effects, it varies as elapsed time squared when the clock error is due to (linear) aging. In filter applications, recalibration is usually not an option. Aging can gradually degrade performance until an end-of-life frequency shift is reached.

Aging Characteristics.

Aging can be positive or negative. Occasionally, a reversal in aging direction is observed. Typical (computer simulated) aging behaviors are illustrated in Fig. 1. The curve showing the reversal is the sum of the other two curves. So far, the simplest proposed aging model showing a reversal consists of two simultaneously acting aging mechanisms, as shown in Fig. 1.

The aging rate of an oscillator is highest when it is first turned on. Since the aging rate during the first few days to weeks is generally significantly higher than during subsequent intervals, the first part of the aging curve is sometimes referred to as "initial aging" or "stabilization period." At a constant temperature, aging usually has an approximately logarithmic dependence on time. When the temperature of a crystal unit is changed, e.g., when an OCXO is turned off, and turned on at a later time, a new aging cycle may start, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 1 - Typical Aging Behaviors.

Figure 2 - Typical Aging Behavior, Including an Interruption (frequency change in parts in 10^9 vs. time in days).

The aging rates of typical commercially available crystal oscillators (in 1991) range from 5 to 10 ppm per year for an inexpensive clock oscillator, to 0.5 to 2 ppm per year for a TCXO, to 0.05 to 0.1 ppm per year for an OCXO. The highest precision OCXOs can age less than 0.01 ppm per year.

Aging Specifications.

Aging is expressed either as a normalized frequency change per unit time after a specified time period, where the unit of time is usually a day, or as a total normalized frequency change over a specified time period. It is necessary to specify a period because aging can be highly nonlinear, especially when a unit is newly fabricated or is first turned on. Examples of aging specifications are: 1) "5 X 10^{-10} per day 7 days after turn-on" for an oven controlled crystal oscillator (OCXO), 2) "1 ppm per year" for a temperature compensated crystal oscillator (TCXO), and 3) "1 ppm to end of 20 year life" for a filter. For non-temperature controlled devices, the temperature at which the aging test is to be performed should also be specified. Guidance for specifying aging can be found in MIL-C-49468 [5] and MIL-O-55310 [1], the "mil-specs"

for precision crystal units and crystal oscillators, respectively, and in a paper by Filler [6].

Aging Mechanisms.

The primary causes of crystal oscillator aging are mass transfer to or from the resonator's surfaces due to adsorption or desorption of contamination, stress relief in the mounting structure of the crystal, changes in the electrodes, package leaks, and changes in the quartz material.

Contamination Transfer Effects: Adsorption, Desorption, Oxidation and Permeation.

Because the frequency of a thickness shear crystal unit, such as an AT-cut or SC-cut unit, is inversely proportional to the thickness of the crystal plate, and because, for example, a typical 5-MHz 3rd overtone plate is on the order of 1 million atomic layers thick, the adsorption or desorption of contamination equivalent to the mass of one atomic layer of quartz changes the frequency by about 1 ppm. In general, if contamination equal in mass to 1 1/2 monolayers of quartz is adsorbed or desorbed from the surfaces, then the frequency change in parts per million is equal to the resonator's frequency in megahertz. In order to achieve low-aging, crystal units must be fabricated and hermetically sealed in ultraclean, ultrahigh vacuum environments, and into packages that are capable of maintaining the clean environment for long periods.

Fig. 3 shows some data on the oxidation of pure nickel in 76 torr of oxygen at 400 °C, 450 °C and 500 °C. Landsberg [7] reviewed and summarized a considerable amount of the type of data plotted in Fig. 3. Besides oxidation, data on adsorption and desorption of many types of gases on many types of solid surfaces were reviewed. For most of the reviewed work, the rates of adsorption, desorption and oxidation depended on the logarithm of the time. Some of the parameters of the log-time model depended strongly on the temperature. In studies of the low temperature (i.e., < 400°C) oxidation of metal films, logarithmic kinetics are usually observed [8]. A molecular model of these processes can produce the observed log-time dependence [7]. It was also pointed out that the rates of some particular systems of this type may not depend on log-time.

The adsorption and desorption of contamination is primarily a function of the nature of the contaminant, the nature of the adsorbing surface, and the temperature. Included in "the nature of the adsorbing surface" is the

crystallographic nature. For example, the adsorption properties of an AT-cut surface are likely to be different from that of an SC- or other cut.

Figure 3 - The Oxidation of Nickel vs. Time.

Leaks into the enclosure, either due to a faulty hermetic seal or to permeation through the enclosure walls, and outgassing of adsorbed and dissolved gases can also result in aging. Even when the hermetic seal is perfect, gases can permeate through the enclosure walls [9,10]. Since most materials used in vacuum and resonator technology exhibit some degree of permeability to gases, maintaining low pressure levels inside the enclosure requires consideration of the permeation characteristics of the enclosure. Hydrogen and helium are notorious for their permeation through metals and glasses, respectively. Even if the permeating gases do not adsorb onto the resonator, if a significant pressure increase occurs, the frequency will change due to the changing hydrostatic pressure in the enclosure [11,12]. When a significant amount of gas leaks into a vacuum sealed resonator, aging can be caused by electrical and mechanical effects caused by changes in the package shape (sometimes called "oil canning," when the package changes with atmospheric pressure changes). Epoxy packages or seals that have been occasionally used in inexpensive resonators are especially susceptible to moisture permeation.

That high amounts of hydrogen permeation can produce aging has been demonstrated [13]. A 5-MHz fundamental

mode resonator, which had copper electrodes, was hermetically sealed, in high vacuum, in a nickel HC-6 enclosure. After the aging of this resonator stabilized, it was immersed in one atmosphere of hydrogen and the aging measurements were continued. Three weeks after immersion, the aging had increased 30-fold, to about 3×10^{-9} per day. After the aging stabilized at this higher rate, the hydrogen was removed. Eight weeks later, the aging rate stabilized at a lower rate, but six months after removal of the hydrogen, the rate was still about five times higher than what it was prior to hydrogen exposure.

Electrode Effects.

Thin films of Au, Ag, Al and Cu are commonly used as electrodes on crystal resonators. The stresses in these films depend on the film material and thickness, and other factors. It has been shown [14] that the film stresses relax with a time constant of a few hours. (The temperature at which the relaxation was measured is not stated explicitly in this reference, but is implied to have been at room temperature. The film thicknesses were 100nm.)

The film stresses also depend strongly on the substrate material and crystallinity (amorphous, crystal surface orientation, etc.), on the substrate cleanliness, temperature, and chemical state, the gases present in the space around the substrate during the deposition process, the purity of the film material, the deposition rate, and on the deposition process (evaporation, sputtering, etc.) [15-20]. In some films, for example, the stress can be varied from tensile to compressive just by varying the background pressure in the vacuum system during deposition [21-23].

Numerous studies have shown that the properties of thin films change with time subsequent to deposition [24-33]. The stability of the film depends on the deposition conditions, especially the substrate temperature, and deposition rate (lower deposition rates under clean conditions usually result in fewer defects), and on the temperatures subsequent to deposition. For example, the resistivity changes in 700Å to 1650Å gold films deposited onto glass microscope slides were found to depend strongly on the substrate temperature [33]. When the films were deposited at 46°C, significant decreases (up to 8.5%) were observed during resistivity measurements, at room temperature, between the fifth hour and the first few weeks after deposition. When the substrate temperature was 112°C during deposition, which is near the recrystallization temperature of 124°C for gold films, the resistivity decreases were much smaller (0.8 to 1.5%). Films, in general, will tend to be more stable if the

substrate temperature during deposition is above the recrystallization temperature of the film material. Deposition at an elevated substrate temperature has a considerably greater stabilization effect than deposition without substrate heating followed by annealing at a later time. The reasons are that diffusion rates are higher at elevated temperatures, and surface diffusion is much faster than bulk diffusion, therefore, the surface atoms have more opportunity to anneal (i.e., move to low energy sites) before they become buried. Similarly, a low deposition rate (under clean conditions) results in a more stable film than a high rate. At very high rates, the surface atoms do not have a chance to anneal before they are buried. High substrate temperatures also contribute to minimizing adsorbed contaminants on the substrate and in the deposited film. If the deposition conditions are not clean, then a slow deposition rate may result in a less stable film due to incorporation of contaminants into the film.

The contribution of electrode stress relief to aging depends on resonator type. SC-cut [34] and electrodeless (e.g., BVA-type [35,36]) resonators are insensitive to such stress relief. For other types of resonators, electrode stress relief can be a contributor, especially to initial aging.

Other types of changes in the electrodes include diffusion effects and chemical reaction effects. For example, when an adhesion layer (such as Cr) is used under a weakly adhering film (such as Au), the two layers can gradually interdiffuse [37,38]. Chemical reactions can occur between the electrode and the quartz surface [16], and between the electrode and the gaseous contaminants in the resonator enclosure. Some metals react chemically with a quartz surface. When the heat of oxide formation is higher for the metal oxide than for SiO_2 , the metal can reduce the SiO_2 to form the metal oxide and produce free silicon at the interface. The heat of oxide formation of α -quartz is -201.34 kcal/mol ($= 8.73 \text{ eV}$), whereas Al_2O_3 's is -399 kcal/mol and Cr_2O_3 's is -270 kcal/mol . Therefore, Al and Cr, two commonly used materials in resonator fabrication, adhere strongly to quartz by forming metal oxides at the metal-quartz interfaces. The formation of Al_2O_3 and free Si at the SiO_2 -Al interface has been demonstrated experimentally [39,40]. Reactions between oxide forming metals and the OH on quartz surfaces also occur.

The properties of thin films can change with time, e.g., the properties of an Al film and of the interface between Al and SiO_2 change with time [41,42]. The changes can be enhanced by temperature, temperature cycling, and the presence of an electric field. These changes can result in

resonator aging.

Highly reactive metals such as Al or Cr are not the preferred electrode materials for low-aging quartz resonators because thin films of such metals produce aging due to: 1) changes at the metal-quartz interfaces, 2) gettering of oxygen and other residual gases inside the enclosure, 3) changes at high strain gradients that exist at electrode edges [43], and 4) changes in the high strains that result from temperature cycling due to the strong adhesion and thermal expansion coefficient differences between the metal film and the quartz. Liquid [44] and plasma [45] anodization have been used in attempts to minimize aging due to oxide growth on the electrodes.

Gold has been the preferred electrode material in the fabrication of low-aging resonators. The reasons for this are that: 1) gold is not highly reactive, it does not form an oxide under normal conditions (clean gold will getter organic contaminants from the air [46], however, such contaminants can be readily removed by UV/ozone cleaning [47]); 2) gold adheres weakly to quartz, the adhesion is strong enough for the electrodes not to be detached by a 36,000 g shock of 12 millisecond duration [48] but is weak enough not to support strain gradients that would show up on X-ray topographs (Cr, Al and Ni films produce strain in the quartz that can be readily seen in X-ray topographs) [43]; and 3) the stresses in pure gold films anneal rapidly [14]. These properties are probably the reason for the fact that the aging of the best long term aging AT-cut resonators with gold electrodes is about the same as that of the best SC-cut and BVA resonators, i.e., a few parts in 10^{12} per day. That the initial aging of the best SC-cut resonators is better than that of the best AT-cuts [49,50] is probably due to the superior insensitivity of the SC-cut to some important types of stresses, such as the stresses due to the electrodes.

It is also possible to make low-aging resonators with copper electrodes [51], however, in one unpublished study [52], although copper plated resonators exhibited low initial aging, the long term aging was poorer than that of similarly fabricated resonators with gold electrodes.

It is well known that, under the influences of high temperatures and high electric fields, electrode materials such as gold and silver will diffuse into the dislocations in quartz [53]. Although diffusion of gold and other electrodes into the quartz has been reported in high-temperature processed resonators [54,55], it is unlikely that such diffusion occurs at normal processing and operating temperatures without the presence of an electric

field. If such diffusion did occur, then the adhesion of, for example, gold on quartz would improve as the resonator ages. Such improved adhesion has not been observed. When five high precision glass enclosed resonators with gold electrodes, which had been fabricated 18 years earlier, were tested, it was found that the gold electrodes could be readily removed with the "Scotch-tape test." Even the weakly adhering "3M Post-it Self-Stick Removable Notes" readily removed these gold electrodes [56]. After removal of the electrodes, with either method, a narrow strip of very thin gold that outlines the perimeter of where the electrodes had been, remained (the strip can be scratched off with tweezers). This strip appears to be the "shadowing" that occurs when an evaporation mask is a finite distance from the quartz plate. The reason for the stronger adhesion of the strip is under investigation. A preliminary analysis of the quartz that had been under the center portion of the electrodes did not indicate the presence of any gold in the quartz. The analysis was performed using SIMS (secondary ion mass spectroscopy).

It has been shown that a DC voltage between the electrodes of a resonator can dramatically increase the initial aging, presumably because of electric field driven diffusion of impurities and electrodes [57]. Although oscillator designers often design circuits which (sometimes inadvertently) place a small DC voltage across the electrodes, one can readily minimize the DC voltage, without lowering the effective Q of the resonator, by placing a capacitor in series and a few megohm resistor in parallel with the resonator [57].

Surface catalytic reactions at silver electrode surfaces, accompanied by the emission of silver atoms, have also been reported to be an aging mechanism in silver-plated resonators [58].

Powerful tools to determine the possible aging contributions of stresses in films associated with particular film fabrication technologies are the form, values, and temperature dependence of the stress relaxation process. Since these parameters of the films are not too difficult to measure directly on actual resonator materials, it is surprising that very few results of this type have been reported for resonator fabrication technologies in current use. Powerful surface analytical tools for detecting diffusion and chemical reaction effects are also available.

Strain/Stress in the Resonator.

Radial forces applied at the perimeter of AT and SC plates shift the frequency [59]. Since the forces applied to the

crystal wafer by the mounting clips and bonding materials are difficult to control and probably change (i.e., relax) with time, resonator aging will depend, to some extent, on the mounts' type, material, and location, on the crystal orientation, and on departures from the design in real resonators. When the bonding process is carried out at high temperatures, the structure is likely to be in equilibrium at a temperature higher than the normal operating temperatures of the resonator. In this case, mismatches in the thermal expansion coefficients of the various materials in the structure will cause stress-induced frequency shifts. When these stresses change with time, aging can result. Bonding materials, such as silver-filled epoxies and polyimides, change dimensions upon curing. This results in further stress changes. The clip forming and welding operations produce residual stresses which are also subject to stress relief.

X-ray topographs can be used to demonstrate the strains caused by a particular mounting clip structure [60,61]. If the strains change with time, aging can result. Radial and tangential thermal coefficients of linear expansion for AT-cut quartz wafers depend on direction. Thermal expansion coefficient differences between the crystal plate and the mounting structure (including the enclosure base) usually result not only in radial stresses on the crystal plate, but also tangential (i.e., torsional) stresses. Resonator structure designs must account for the differences in thermal expansion coefficients between the various parts of the resonator assembly to minimize temperature dependent stresses applied to the resonator.

Since stresses are inevitable, the materials used in the mounting structure of low-aging resonators should anneal either very rapidly, or very slowly, i.e., be either perfectly soft or perfectly elastic. Materials which anneal very rapidly are usually not a viable option because such materials generally result in unacceptable behavior under shock and vibration. Mounting structures that are nearly stress-free have been developed [35,62].

The slow and progressive deformation of a material under constant stress is called creep. Creep is observed in metals, glasses, polymers, and even in single crystals. Metals usually exhibit creep at a temperature greater than $0.4 T_m$, where T_m is the metal's melting point in degrees Kelvin [63,64]. The rate of creep, especially in amorphous materials, and organic materials such as the epoxies commonly used for bonding crystals, is highly sensitive to temperature. Numerous alloys have been developed for high resistance to stress relief, for electrical connector and other spring applications. Mounting clips

made of such alloys can serve to minimize aging due to stress relief in the mounting structure, as can designs that use carefully oriented quartz for mounting [35], and for the enclosure [65].

The amount of aging produced by a given amount of stress relief is a function of the orientation of the mounting clips with respect to the crystallographic axes of the quartz plate, and the types of stresses [59]. For in-plane diametric forces, the force-frequency coefficient K_f vs. azimuth angle ψ has been found to have zeroes for all the commonly used cuts, such as the AT- and SC-cuts [59]. Therefore, one might conclude that aging due to stress relief in the mounting clips can be eliminated by mounting the crystals where $K_f = 0$. Unfortunately, it is difficult to completely eliminate aging due to stress relief in the mounting structure because: 1) the azimuthal angles where $K_f = 0$ are functions of temperature [66], so that the mounting point orientations would have to be different for resonators of different turnover temperatures, 2) the ψ where the effects of bonding stresses are zero is different from the ψ where the $K_f = 0$, at least for the AT-cut, the only cut for which bonding stress effects have been reported [67], and 3) the forces due to mounting clips are generally not purely in-plane diametric forces. This is especially true for three and four-point mounted resonators because, since the thermal expansion coefficient of quartz is highly anisotropic whereas that of the typical package base is isotropic, the forces due to thermal expansion coefficient mismatches will have tangential components. In two-point mounted resonators also, the base's thermal expansion applies torsional-type forces in addition to the in-plane diametric forces.

Even when the mounting stresses are made negligible, the bonding stresses alone can cause significant frequency shifts, which, upon annealing, can cause aging [67]. The temperature coefficient of frequency will also change with large changes in stress. In these cases, measuring temperature coefficients along with the aging can be used to determine whether or not stress relief is a significant aging mechanism.

Diffusion Effects.

Although it is likely that diffusion processes cause aging in resonators, very few authors have reported analyses of aging in terms of diffusion [4,68]. Solid-solid diffusion processes can occur between the electrodes and the quartz, within the quartz itself, and in the mounting and electrical attachments; gas-solid diffusion processes can be rate determining steps for some processes occurring at the

resonator surface. Another conceivable aging mechanism is the diffusion of impurities in the quartz to dislocations and surfaces.

The rate of a simple diffusion-controlled process in an isotropic medium is given by [69]

$$\text{Rate} = -D * \text{concentration gradient}, \quad (1)$$

where D, the diffusion constant, is

$$D = \frac{mh}{A(d_2 - d_1)t},$$

m is the mass of the diffusing material, h is the thickness of the slab in which the diffusion is occurring, A is the area participating in the diffusion, and d_2 and d_1 are the concentrations (mass per unit volume) of the diffusing material on the two sides of the slab [69,70].

Table I shows diffusion constants at room temperature for some metals commonly used as electrodes or attachments in resonators [70]:

Table I

Metal System	D (cm ² /sec)
Al into Cu	1.75 X 10 ⁻²
Au into Cu	4 to 16 X 10 ⁻²
Cu into Ag	5.95 X 10 ⁻⁵
Ni into Cu	6.5 X 10 ⁻⁵
Pd into Cu	1.6 X 10 ⁻⁴

This short table shows that diffusion rates of potential interest to crystal suppliers vary by orders of magnitude depending on the metals involved in the diffusion.

The movements of point defects in the quartz lattice have energies and activation energies of 0.03 eV to 0.154 eV [71]. Although these activation energies are similar in magnitude to observed aging activation energies [72], the validity of a direct comparison has not yet been established.

Diffusion processes often have an approximately power dependence on time, with the power being about 0.5 [72]. For some diffusion configurations, the diffusion rate equation also contains an exponential time factor [72].

Diffusion rates are usually thermally activated, with an Arrhenius dependence on temperature [10,73]. The

activation energy for Cu into Al (33.9 kcal/mole) seems higher than most reported aging activation energies [72]. However, the activation energy for grain boundary diffusion of Ag into Ag is 21.5 kcal/mole, which is not much higher than the reported aging activation energies [72,73].

Changes in the Quartz.

Changes in the quartz due to stresses or other causes could lead to aging, although no reports of such changes (at normal temperatures and pressures) could be found in the literature. Perfect quartz would not be expected to change with time (by definition). The imperfections that are subject to change include surface and point defects, dislocations, impurities, inclusions, and twins. Surface defects, such as the microcracks produced by lapping, can change with time, however, by properly etching the surfaces subsequent to mechanical treatment [74], the possibility of changes can be greatly reduced.

It is unlikely that dislocation motion due to stresses is a factor in aging at typical operating temperatures, although dislocation motion can occur at high temperatures and pressures [75]. Even in sweeping experiments [76] which are usually conducted far above the normal operating temperatures of oscillators, no evidence of dislocation motion has been reported. The energy needed to anneal quartz damage due to neutron irradiation may be a clue to the energies needed to move dislocations. When quartz is irradiated with fast neutrons, displacement damage occurs. At high doses, the quartz gradually becomes disordered into an amorphous form. Annealing studies on neutron-damaged quartz indicate that the annealing temperature of quartz is above the inversion temperature [77,78]. The activation energy for structure annealing is 0.75 eV.

The outgassing of quartz is another possible aging mechanism, the magnitude of which is unknown. Although a large amount of information is available on the outgassing characteristics of vitreous SiO₂ [9,10], no reports on the outgassing characteristics of α -quartz were found. Presumably, since all materials outgas to some extent, α -quartz does too. Another unknown is the extent to which impurities in the quartz diffuse to dislocations and surfaces at normal operating temperatures. Quartz is known to contain impurities that are subject to diffusion [79]. The impurity that is present in highest concentrations is hydrogen. Natural and cultured quartz both contain hydrogen, in amounts ranging from 200 ppm to 2500 ppm relative to Si (3 ppm to 42 ppm by weight).

Circuit Aging and Other Electrical Aging.

The oscillator circuit includes electrical elements that are subject to change. These elements determine some important operating factors, such as resonator load reactance, dc bias, and drive level. Changes in these electrical elements and factors cause oscillator aging. Stray reactance changes due to movements of the electrical leads and the gradual deformation of circuit boards and enclosure walls also produce frequency changes. For example, in a 22-MHz fundamental mode AT-cut resonator, a lead length change of 0.005 mm results in a frequency change of 1×10^{-9} [6], and a load capacitance aging of 1 ppm per day causes oscillator aging of parts in 10^{10} per day. Capacitors can age due to the effects of humidity and temperature; e.g., humidity can change the dielectric constants and loss factors of capacitors and circuit boards. Inductors are notorious for their instabilities; e.g., the windings of inductors can stretch and move, especially during temperature changes. In one study [80], capacitors of various types aged 3 ppm/day to 70 ppm/day, and a 2 μ H coil custom wound on a phenolic form (for high stability) aged 2 ppm/day. Amplifiers and varactors can also change with time. Drive level changes can result in frequency changes on the order of 10^{-7} per ma^2 [81]. Significant improvements in medium and long term stability can often be obtained by hermetically sealing the oscillator to minimize the frequency instabilities due to changes in humidity and atmospheric pressure [82,83].

As was previously noted in the "Electrode Effects" section, a DC voltage between the electrodes of a resonator can dramatically increase the initial aging of a resonator, presumably because of electric field driven diffusion of impurities and electrodes. Oscillator designers often design circuits which (sometimes inadvertently) place a small DC voltage across the electrodes. When high stability TCXOs from several manufacturers were examined, DC voltages ranging from a fraction of a volt to about 4 volts were found. The DC voltage effect can be easily minimized, without a significant lowering of the resonator's effective Q, by placing a capacitor in series and a few megohm resistor in parallel with the resonator [57].

DC voltages can also result from static charges generated during fabrication. Static charges can result in high (> 1 kV) voltages. Since the surface resistivity of clean quartz is high, the "static" charges can take a long time to decay. This can lead to (initial) aging, especially in doubly rotated crystals, such as SC-cuts, which can have

sensitivities of parts in 10^{-9} per volt. Well-known static ("ESD") control measures can be used to minimize this problem.

In OCXOs, aging of the temperature control circuitry can change the set point of the oven, resulting in aging. The amount of aging for a given set point change depends on the frequency vs. temperature characteristic of the resonator, and will, in general, be much smaller for a typical SC-cut OCXO than for an AT-cut one [84].

Temperature and Temperature-Cycling Dependence of Aging.

Although most of the known aging mechanisms are thermally activated, the expected strong temperature dependence of aging rates has not been observed in many medium stability and high stability resonators. For example, in one study of eight AT-cut resonator types, from several manufacturers, the resonators were aged at room temperature, 85°C and 120°C. No systematic aging rate variations with temperature were found [85]. The resonators did not always exhibit a higher aging rate at elevated temperatures; some even aged at a lower rate at the elevated temperatures. The resonators ranged from 14.4-MHz fundamental mode to 70-MHz third overtone.

In another study, groups of resonators were aged at 50°C, 60°C and 70°C. It was found that, although the aging improved for many resonators when the temperature was lower, the low-aging rate resonators did not change their aging characteristics notably when the temperature was lowered [86].

When groups of low and medium stability resonators were aged at various temperatures ranging from 25°C to 100°C, the aging rates were found to increase with increasing temperatures [87]. The increases varied with crystal type. A conclusion the authors draw concerning aging prediction is "that such prognosis will be sufficiently reliable only when the crystal unit will operate under more or less identical conditions during all its service life. If the ambient temperature or drive level changes, even the sign of frequency aging may change." In some earlier studies on precision 2.5-MHz 5th overtone AT-cut resonators [88], and 550-kHz wire mounted DT-cut resonators [89], an increase in aging temperature increased the aging rates.

The aging of groups of six high precision SC-cut resonators and two high precision AT-cut resonators were measured successively at the lower turnover point (LTP) and upper turnover point (UTP) temperatures. The UTP

to LTP differences ranged from 19°C to 40°C for the SC-cuts, and it was about 100°C for the AT-cuts. The higher aging temperatures at the UTP introduced a small positive aging contribution to the SC-cuts' aging, i.e., the aging of both positive and negative aging resonators became more positive at the UTP. The results for the AT-cuts indicated no drastic improvements in aging rates at the LTP [57]. Aging at the SC-cuts' UTPs, which ranged up to 120°C, did not cause a significant aging rate degradation [57,90].

If aging were due to a single thermally activated process, then one ought to be able to observe phenomenally low-aging rates by cooling the resonators to cryogenic temperatures. Although the definitive aging experiment at low temperatures is yet to be performed, the limited data at such temperatures indicates no drastic improvements in aging rates [91-93]. When the aging of high precision SC-cut resonators was measured at (the lower turnover) temperatures in the vicinity of -10°C and compared with the aging of similarly fabricated resonators aged at turnover temperatures that were 90°C to 120°C higher, no significant improvement in aging was observed at the lower temperatures [57,94].

When an aging interruption is accompanied by a significant temperature excursion, the effects can range from drastic to small. For an example of drastic change, when the aging of an oscillator containing a high precision 5-MHz 5th overtone glass enclosed AT-cut resonator was interrupted and the oscillator was cooled to -40°C for nine days, the aging rate increased drastically subsequent to the resumption of aging. Months elapsed before the aging rate returned to its value prior to the interruption. Fig. 4 shows this example. This oscillator was aging at an approximately constant rate of -1.1×10^{-11} per day prior to interruption. After the aging resumed: 1) the aging rate became positive at first, 2) the rate reversed direction after about 150 days, and 3) the aging rate stabilized at -4.0×10^{-12} per day after about one year and it stayed at that rate for the subsequent four years.

Low temperature storage can produce drastic aging rate changes (and frequency offsets) in SC-cut oscillators, too [57,90]. In another aging experiment, groups of high stability OCXOs and TCXOs were on-off cycled and temperature cycled during the experiment. For most of the oscillators, the interruptions did not worsen the total frequency changes during the aging period [94]. Similarly, when high stability microcomputer compensated crystal oscillators were aged with repeated interruptions for temperature cycling, the aging rates were not made

worse by the cyclings [95].

It has been shown that stability under intermittent operation is dependent on the processes used in fabricating the resonator. For example, upon restarting an oscillator following an oven shutdown, those containing high temperature processed crystal units exhibit much smaller frequency offsets, and the aging rates return to their pre-shutdown values much faster, than do low temperature processed units [89,96].

Figure 4 - The Effect of Aging Interruption.

Frequency and Overtone Dependence of Aging.

Since most of the known aging mechanisms are associated with the resonator's surfaces, it is not surprising that, in general, resonators of higher volume-to-surface ratio tend to exhibit a lower aging rate than resonators of lower volume-to-surface ratio. For a given fabrication process, the aging rate tends to scale with the volume-to-surface ratio of the resonator's active area, i.e., with the frequency of the plate. For example, the aging of 333-MHz fundamental mode SC-cut resonators [97] at 25°C (the test OCXOs were kept in a freezer to permit stabilization of the OCXO ovens at 25°C) was found to range from 1 to 3×10^{-8} per day after one year of continuous aging [98]. The aging of comparably fabricated 5-MHz fundamental mode resonators under the same aging conditions would typically be on the order of 333/5 times lower, i.e., on the order of a few parts in 10^{10} per day. The scaling with frequency appears to apply to SAW devices too; e.g., the aging rates of "good" 500-MHz SAW resonators [99] are typically on the order of 100 times higher than the aging rates of "good" 5-MHz bulk acoustic wave resonators.

The aging rates of 2.5-MHz and 5-MHz 5th overtone AT-cut resonators made according to designs and processes

developed by Warner and coworkers in the late-1950's and 1960's [88,89,96,100-104] are still difficult to surpass. This is probably due, in part, to the large volume-to-surface ratio of these resonators. No larger volume-to-surface ratio resonators have been developed since. (In fact, 2.5-MHz 5th overtone resonators are no longer made regularly.)

In general, overtone resonator aging rates are lower than aging rates of comparably fabricated fundamental resonators of the same frequency. The reasons are, not only that overtone resonators have a larger volume-to-surface ratio, but also, that overtone resonators, having a smaller C_1 , exhibit a lower aging rate due to oscillator circuit component aging and a lower sensitivity to changes at the resonators' edges.

Drive Level Dependence of Aging.

The experimental evidence concerning the effect of drive level is mixed. In one report on the aging of (low stability) 32.8-kHz flexural mode resonators [87], an increase to "inadmissibly high values of crystal unit drive level," from 10 μ W to 100 μ W, produced a significant increase in aging rates. (An increase in aging temperature was also found to increase the aging rates of these resonators.) The report, however, references an earlier study which showed "the absence of any amount of significant influence of drive conditions on the crystal unit aging..." at reasonable drive levels.

The aging rate of AT-cut resonators has been reported to be degraded by high drive levels [105]. Increasing the current through 2.5- and 5-MHz 5th overtone resonators ten fold from 75 μ A resulted in an increase in monthly aging rate from 1×10^{-10} to 1.5×10^{-9} . The aging of BVA resonators has also been reported to be sensitive to drive level [106,107]. The drive level sensitivity has been used to produce oscillators that exhibit "zero aging" at a particular time. (It is highly unlikely, however, that such a balancing of aging mechanisms can last for long periods.)

Changing the resonator drive levels in discrete steps did not affect the aging rates of precision, high temperature processed SC-cut resonators, up to a 2.5-mA drive current (594 μ W), the maximum that was tried in the study [94].

Since resonator frequency is a function of drive level [81], if the oscillator circuitry ages so as to gradually change the drive level, oscillator aging can result. At very high drive levels, the power dissipation in the resonator will

raise the temperature of the resonator's active area. Therefore, resonators which are adversely affected by increased aging temperatures would also be expected to be adversely affected by increased drive levels. From the limited data available, it appears that, at a constant drive level, the aging of low stability and AT-cut resonators is adversely affected by high drive levels, whereas that of precision SC-cuts is not affected. (It may be worthwhile to repeat the measurement of the drive level dependence of precision AT-cuts, in carefully designed oscillators, to eliminate the possibility that the drive level dependence of aging was circuit induced, e.g., via higher DC bias on the resonator at higher drive levels.)

Increasing the drive level increases the displacements, velocities and accelerations of particles at resonator surfaces. At high frequencies, especially, particle accelerations can be on the order of a million g's. High drive levels' ability to remove particulate contamination from surfaces is well known. Whether or not high drive levels can affect the desorption of adsorbed contaminants has been considered [108]. Since the increased kinetic energy of an adsorbed molecule due to a high drive level is very much less than 20 kcal/mol (which is the typical adsorption energy of concern), and is also much less than the thermal energies at normal operating temperatures, high drive levels probably do not directly affect adsorption-desorption phenomena.

The Effects of Aging Interruptions.

If during an interruption in aging the resonator or oscillator experiences a change in its environment, then upon resuming the aging, the aging rate can be significantly different from what it was prior to the interruption. The effects of thermal interruptions, drive level changes, and DC fields were discussed earlier. Other interruptions that can result in increased aging include mechanical and thermal shock, vibration, magnetic and electric fields, AC signals, and radiation [109,110]. Few studies have been reported on the effects of interruptions other than thermal. In general, the effects will depend on the nature of the interruption, and on the aging mechanisms that are disturbed by the interruption. For example, if during a shock some elastic limit in the resonator's mounting structure is exceeded, then the shock may change the stress-relief component of aging. Similarly, if a radiation pulse displaces impurities to higher energy sites in the lattice, then the subsequent aging may be affected by the migration of impurities to low energy sites.

Dependence of Aging on Material and Mode Type.

Since there are very few reports on common applications that use different materials or modes, the effects of material and mode type on aging are not easily separable. No reports on the effects of changing material for the same mode type were found in the literature. No reports on aging for bulk wave devices made from lithium niobate, berlinite, or other new piezoelectric materials were found. In this section, aging data on extensional mode lead zirconate titanate and lithium tantalate resonators, other modes using lead zirconate titanate, hydrophones made from poly (vinylidene fluoride), quartz flexural tuning forks, and quartz surface wave resonators are presented. Where possible, the material effects are separated from the device type effects.

Dependence of Aging on Resonator Material.

Extensional resonators made from lead zirconate titanate and similar materials age from 700 to 10000 ppm per decade in time [111]. Improved lead zirconate titanate type materials operating in all modes age about 1000 ppm to end-of-life of 10 years [112].

For piezoelectric ceramic materials the aging usually proceeds as log-time [113] and is therefore reported as a frequency change per decade of time. No recent reports with a detailed description of the time and temperature dependence of aging in materials like lead zirconate titanate could be found.

Extensional mode lithium tantalate resonators, with frequencies from 455-kHz to 2-MHz, were aged at room temperature for more than 900 days. Aging did not depend significantly on frequency. The frequency decreased about 100 ppm during the first year; after two years, the aging rate was 3×10^{-7} per month [114].

Hydrophones made from a plastic piezoelectric polymer, poly (vinylidene fluoride) age a few 10000 ppm per decade in time, with an upper temperature limitation of 80°C [115]. For the hydrophone aging, the mode of vibration used was not stated, but it was implied that this aging value was determined for the 31 and 33 modes.

Most reported aging studies have been for quartz and lead zirconate titanate devices.

Dependence of Aging on Mode Type.

Some reports on aging of low frequency and high

frequency quartz bulk wave devices, as well as the aging of surface acoustic wave (SAW) resonators and delay lines, are summarized by Gerber [4].

The aging of low frequency wire mounted quartz crystal resonators operating in different contour (length-width) modes was reported by Armstrong, et al. [89], and by Gerber and Sykes [116]. For these devices the aging proceeded as log-time.

Kanbayashi [117], Engdahl and Matthey [118], Yoda [119], and Forrer [120] have reported aging results for quartz flexural mode tuning forks at frequencies of about 32.768-kHz. Yoda reported aging results for 32.768-kHz flexural (XY, NT, tuning fork) mode resonators to be ± 5 ppm per year. Some examples of -0.2 to +0.3 ppm per year were shown [121]. Table II summarizes the aging of several types of low frequency quartz resonators.

The data in Table II suggest that flexural and width-shear resonators age less than extensional or face shear resonators. The data in Table II also suggest that lower frequency resonators age less than higher frequency resonators of the same type. From the data in Table II, it

is not possible to assign the cause of the low-aging flexures and width-shears to mode type or frequency alone.

Gerber [4] also summarized some reports on the aging of quartz surface acoustic wave resonators and delay lines. For some 184- and 194-MHz SAW resonators there was little or no difference in aging at 50°C to 150°C, but increased aging was observed at 200°C to 250°C [122,123]. For some 160-MHz SAW resonators powered in an oscillator at 60°C the log-time aging rates approached 1×10^{-9} per day; -5 to $+5 \times 10^{-9}$ per day after 162 days. According to the general rule that the aging is proportional to the frequency, these SAW resonators had an aging equivalent to a bulk wave resonator of about 6×10^{-10} per day at 10-MHz. For these devices the best long term aging was -0.64 to -0.31 ppm per year [124-126]. For 160-MHz SAW resonators, aging data were best fitted with two simultaneous log-time aging mechanisms [125,126].

Some 300-MHz SAW resonators had aging rates of 1 to 2 ppm per 30 days at room temperature [127]. Some 1.4-GHz SAW delay lines aged several ppm in 52 weeks,

Table II
Aging of Low Frequency Quartz Crystal Resonator
(Probably at room temperature)

Mode Type (frequency)	Aging (ppm)	Time of Aging
Extensional (200-kHz)	8.0	100 days
Face Shear (200-kHz)	4.0	100 days
Extensional (100-kHz)	3.0	100 days
Width-Shear (990-kHz)	3.0	100 days
Flexure (8-kHz)	1.2	100 days
Flexure (445-kHz to 2-MHz)	-0.2 to +0.3	365 days
Width-Shear (550-kHz)	1.0	100 days
Width-Shear (230-kHz)	0.5	100 days
Flexural Tuning Fork (32.768-kHz)	-0.5 to +2.0	365 days

also probably at room temperature [128]; 200- to 400-MHz SAW delay lines in powered oscillators at about 30°C aged between -10 to +17 ppm in about 60 to 120 weeks [129]; 400-MHz SAW devices aged less than 1 ppm per year (-2 to +4 ppm per year) on a production basis [130,131]; 187-MHz to 425-MHz SAW resonator oscillators operating at room temperature aged between 0.1 and 0.5 ppm per year with aging times from 27 weeks to 80 weeks [65]; 425-MHz SAW resonator oscillators aged less than 0.1 ppm in 100 weeks at 60°C [99].

A survey of aging for SAW devices showed best aging rates of less than 0.1 ppm per year [131]. SAW aging continues to be reduced as the SAW fabrication technology adopts bulk wave processes of cleanliness, high temperature processing, and careful attention to the selection of materials, mountings, and packages.

Low-aging Oscillators: The State of the Art, Present and Future.

The lowest aging rates reported to date are a few parts in 10^{13} per day [90,105]. The date of reference number 105 is 1967. Unfortunately, the authors cite unpublished results obtained elsewhere. The aging rate of the parts in 10^{13} per day oscillator of reference number 90 had increased to 4×10^{-12} per day one year after publication of the reference, and remained at that rate for the next year (and is continuing at that rate as of mid-1991)[98].

Several authors have reported few parts in 10^{12} per day aging rates [36,88,90,94,96,100,132,133]. Such aging has been reported for only a few resonators, usually after extended stabilization periods. No manufacturer will guarantee such aging today even though the first report of parts in 10^{12} aging (1×10^{-10} per month) appeared in 1958 [100].

The slow progress in the best long term aging performance is puzzling because during the past 30 years, numerous advancements have taken place which ought to have yielded improvements. Among the advancements are: the SC-cut, better ultrahigh vacuum systems, better cleaning techniques, better understanding of stress effects, and better oscillator circuitry. These advancements seem to have resulted in significant improvements in initial aging, but not in the long term aging. As manufacturers adopted these advancements, the advancements have also resulted in improvements in the aging of resonators in high volume production.

In 1983-84, an informal survey of worldwide capabilities

in making low-aging resonators was performed [57]. Ten organizations were identified which could make resonators with parts in 10^{11} per day aging after 30 days of continuous operation. Although the processes used to make these resonators varied widely, the end results with respect to long term aging did not (the stabilization periods, however, were much shorter for some than for others).

Parts in 10^{11} aging has been achieved with AT-, BT- and SC-cut resonators; with glass enclosed, metal enclosed, and ceramic flatpack enclosed resonators; with natural, cultured and swept cultured quartz; with lightly etched and deeply etched resonator plates; with mechanically polished and chemically polished plates; etc. A high temperature vacuum bake prior to sealing the resonators appeared to be the key step that was common to all the processes that produced low-aging. Although the bake temperatures, times and vacuum conditions varied widely, it is clear from the survey and other evidence, that vacuum baking before sealing is a necessary step in the production of low-aging resonators.

Aside from high temperature processing, the only parameter that was, in some respects, common to all the processes was the quartz material. No significant improvements in reducing quartz defects, such as dislocations and hydrogen content, have taken place during the past 30 years. In fact, the dislocation densities in cultured quartz have probably increased over the years. Since the quality of commercially available cultured quartz is adequate for nearly all high-volume applications, and since it is expensive for growers to "refresh" the seeds periodically by using natural quartz, the growers have had little incentive for refreshing seeds. If the seeds are not refreshed, cultured quartz grown on successive generations of cultured quartz seeds will contain increasing densities of dislocations. Although no data could be found on the defect densities in low-aging resonators from 30 years ago vs. today, it is conceivable that the aging of the lowest aging resonators is somehow related to quartz defects. The outgassing of quartz may also limit the lowest attainable aging.

Another parameter that is common to all resonators is background ionizing radiation due to cosmic rays and radioactive trace elements in the soil and building materials. The amount of background radiation depends on location. The average annual radiation dose from natural sources in the U.S.A. has been reported to be on the order of 0.1 rad [134].

The radiation sensitivities of resonators are a highly nonlinear function of dose at low doses. The low dose radiation effects are not well understood. The frequency changes per rad at low doses can be several orders of magnitude higher than at high doses [135]; sensitivity as high as 1×10^{-9} per rad has been reported upon initial irradiations [110]. A resonator with such sensitivity would exhibit apparent aging (i.e., drift, according to the new definitions [2]) of 1×10^{-10} per year or 3×10^{-13} per day due to the background radiation. Although other resonators have been found to have smaller sensitivities [109], and the radiation was deposited much faster in the experiments than the rate of deposition of background radiation, since the low dose effects are not well understood, and the rate dependencies at very low rates are unknown, it is conceivable that the effects of background radiation are not negligible in the lowest aging resonators. A better understanding of low dose effects (and the means to minimize these effects) may be a prerequisite to making substantial improvements in the technology of ultra low-aging resonators.

To achieve the lowest aging rates, the oscillator circuitry must also be carefully designed. Achieving lower than parts in 10^{12} per day oscillator stabilities is no easy task, however; the best circuits do not yet seem to limit the achievable long term aging of small C_1 resonators, such as 5-MHz 5th overtone SC-cuts. (Some of the lowest aging rates reported have been for 10-MHz 3rd overtone SC-cut oscillators [57,94].)

In spite of the lack of significant progress in improving the aging of the lowest aging oscillators, no evidence exists to indicate that the barriers to further improvements are insurmountable. The definitive experiments, in which all known aging mechanisms are minimized, are yet to be done.

Aging Acceleration Effects.

Multiple Aging Mechanism Pitfall.

The temperature dependence of aging rate depends on the processes used during a resonator's fabrication. Since the aging rates due to most known aging mechanisms have strong (e.g., exponential) dependencies on temperature, care must be taken in the use and interpretation of accelerated aging tests. Especially when two or more aging mechanisms are present, simple accelerated aging tests can lead to misleading or meaningless results [57,136].

For example, adsorption and desorption of contamination is believed to be a significant aging mechanism in many resonators. The half-life, $t_{1/2}$, of adsorbed molecules can be expressed as

$$t_{1/2} = t_0 e^{E_d/RT} \quad (2)$$

where R is the gas constant, t_0 is about 10^{-13} seconds, E_d is the desorption energy, and T is the temperature in Kelvins [9]. Therefore, the half-life of a molecule at room temperature ($25^\circ\text{C} = 398^\circ\text{K}$), is about 1/2 minute when $E_d = 20$ kcal/mol; it is 30 years when $E_d = 30$ kcal/mol, and it is a billion years when $E_d = 40$ kcal/mol. Molecules that have $E_d = 20$ kcal/mol are desorbed relatively rapidly and are pumped away during processing in vacuum. A monolayer of molecules (with molecular weight comparable to that of quartz) with $E_d = 30$ kcal/mol contributes on the order of 10^{-9} per day to the aging of, e.g., 20-MHz fundamental mode AT-cut resonators. A monolayer of molecules with $E_d = 40$ kcal/mol contributes on the order of 10^{-17} per day, and can, therefore, be considered to be stable with time. Therefore, only a few molecular species are likely to contribute to aging (but these include some important ones, such as H_2O , CO_2 , CO and CH_4).

In Eq. 2, E_d is sometimes found to increase with decreasing coverage, and after a monolayer is formed, it is generally also different for a second adsorbed layer. Although Eq. 2 gives the half-life of the desorption process, the details of the time dependence of desorption are not specifically included. This detail is supplied by an analysis such as the ones by Landsberg [7] and Glang, et al.[9].

If, for instance, a resonator's aging is determined by the desorption of two species of contaminants, one with $E_d = 30$ kcal/mol and the other with $E_d = 40$ kcal/mol, then accelerated aging at, for example, 150°C will provide meaningless results. At 150°C , the molecules with $E_d = 30$ kcal/mol, which are the molecules that determine the aging at room temperature, are desorbed within a fraction of a second. The subsequent aging is then determined by the $E_d = 40$ kcal/mol molecules, which at room temperature do not contribute measurably to the aging. The 150°C aging results, therefore, will not shed any light on the aging that can be expected at room temperature. Data at several temperatures is necessary to reveal the presence of multiple aging mechanisms and their effect on the aging at the normal operating temperatures.

Brief Review of the Theory of Rate Processes.

The following tutorial discussion of rate processes [137] is included in this review paper because understanding rate processes can be important in our attempts to understand aging and accelerated aging results.

The various aging mechanisms are specific cases of rate processes. Many studies of chemical rate processes have been reported and are summarized in textbooks on physical chemistry and chemical rate processes. Early studies of chemical reaction rates were on gas and solution systems.

For gas reactions, the reaction rate is often controlled by collisions between reacting gas atoms and molecules. Arrhenius proposed that the reaction rate could be expressed as:

$$\text{Reaction Rate} = K e^{-E_a/RT} \quad (3)$$

where E_a was called the activation energy because it described the dependence of rate on the absolute temperature in degrees Kelvin (T). T is the resonator temperature, sometimes called the soak temperature. R was a constant that made the exponent argument unitless, as required. If $R = 1$ then E_a is in degrees Kelvin; R can be selected so that E_a is in electron volts (a common unit often used in studies of the aging of semiconductor devices), or calories or kilocalories per mole (which is a common unit used in chemical reaction rate studies). K includes factors specific to the system of interest, such as gas reactant types and pressures or dissolved reactant types and concentrations.

Boltzmann later developed a statistical thermodynamic theory of gas reactions that showed that E_a in the Arrhenius proposal ought to depend on temperature because it had a part associated with the distribution of system energy (entropy) as well as the part associated with changes in the average system energy (thermal energy). According to this theory E_a should really be F_a , the change in the free energy of the reaction process (rather than the change in the enthalpy). This more rigorous theory helped to make sense of a larger set of experimental results, including those of a few reactions which were actually slower at higher temperatures. These particular reactions had rates controlled by the distribution of thermal energy rather than by the average change in the thermal energy. Further studies of gas phase reaction rates have included quantum effects for simple systems.

Experimental studies have shown that reactions in solutions are more complicated than gas phase reactions. Experimental studies have also shown that reactions involving the interaction of a gas or dissolved reactant with a surface are generally more complicated than either gas or solution phase reactions. In spite of the additional complexity, the gas phase ideas of reaction rates controlled by an Arrhenius or Boltzmann rate law and by collisions between reacting atoms, molecules, free radicals, and surfaces, have been very useful in developing an understanding of general reaction rates.

This brief history of reaction rate science suggests that oversimplification can easily lead to an inadequate understanding of the processes being considered. For example, it was found experimentally that many gas and solution phase reactions have Arrhenius activation energies that produce a doubling of the rate for every ten degrees Celsius increase in reaction temperature. If no other evidence is available, this activation energy can be used to design experiments to efficiently estimate the actual activation energy for the system of interest. Credible long term estimates of crystal resonator and crystal oscillator aging can only be determined from these experimentally determined activation energies and not by the general rule of thumb.

For many gas and solution systems, the dependence of the concentration of a reactant or resultant species on time is exponential, giving a reaction rate that can approach zero, as a reacting species is completely used up in the reaction. In systems for which one of the reacting species has a very large excess concentration, so that the concentration does not change very much during the entire reaction process, changing the concentration of that species may not measurably change the reaction rate.

A Log-time Law of Chemisorption, Oxidation, and Stress Relief.

A review of chemisorption on metal surfaces and oxidation of metal surfaces [7], two processes which could easily affect the dependence of the frequency of a crystal resonator on time, showed how most of the available experimental data were consistent with a logarithmic rate law. The source of such a law was also proposed. In spite of some uncertainties, most of the available metal chemisorption and oxidation experimental data could be described by:

$$q = \left(\frac{1}{b}\right) \log \left[\frac{t+t_0}{t_0} \right] \quad (4)$$

where q is the amount of adsorbed gas, t is the time, and b and t_0 are constants. In Eq. 4 t_0 is not the starting time for the adsorption, but is one of two parameters that characterize the aging process (t_0 will be used as the aging process starting time in a later section of this paper).

At least that part of the aging of crystal devices associated with chemisorption of contaminant gases on the crystal surfaces, or on the electrodes, or with the oxidation of the electrode material, or the quartz itself, might have a logarithmic rate law. Some quartz resonator designers have recognized that many resonators age a fixed amount per decade in time, which is a logarithmic rate dependence [4,6,68,71,89,96,104,138-142].

The atomistic/molecular model of the chemisorption process with a logarithmic rate law was expressed in terms of the specialized language of adsorption chemistry, but can be stated in much simpler and more general terms. The simpler and more general statements are that: 1) the adsorption does not depend on any concentrations (zero order), and 2) that the Arrhenius activation energy is a linear function of the amount of adsorption. Both of these statements can be expressed as:

$$\frac{dq}{dt} = C e^{-(E_{a0} + \langle E_{a1}q \rangle)/kT} \quad (5)$$

where q is the amount of adsorbed material (proportional to the frequency shift in a resonator due to adsorbed material), t is the time, T is the soak temperature in degrees Kelvin, C does not depend on time or temperature, E_{a0} and E_{a1} are the constant and linear components of the activation energy, and k determines the units of E_{a0} and E_{a1} . For example, if E_{a0} is expressed in degrees Kelvin and E_{a1} is expressed in degrees Kelvin per second, then $k = 1$ and t is in seconds. Only a few studies on the use of Eq. 4 in the analysis of aging of resonators using quartz or other piezoelectric materials have been reported [4,6,68,71,89,96,104,138-142].

Before examining several implications of Eq. 5, we should note that thermal stress relaxation in metals such as zinc [143] has also been reported to follow a logarithmic rate law [7], as does the oxidation of many metals [8]. Consequently, even if the logarithmic rate law were established as valid for crystal aging, other evidence

would be needed to separate the effects of the chemisorption, oxidation, and thermal stress relaxation parts of the aging in the resonator [72]. The authors do not know about any other proposed mechanism for the aging of crystal resonators for which a basis as good as that of the logarithmic time mechanism has been developed.

Implication of the Log-time Aging Law.

An important question is: under what conditions can Eq. 5 be used to understand and control the aging of resonators? A careful examination of the consequences of Eq. 5 is one place to start developing an answer to this question.

Integrating Eq. 5 from t_0 to t and $q(t_0)$ to $q(t)$ gives:

$$q(t) = q(t_0) + \frac{kT}{E_{a1}} \ln[1 + \langle B(t-t_0) \rangle] \quad (6)$$

$$\text{where } B = \frac{E_{a1} C}{kT e^{\left[\frac{E_{a0} + [E_{a1}q(t_0)]}{kT} \right]}}$$

Eq. 6 describes the dependence of q on time and soak temperature. In Eq. 6, t_0 is the starting time for the process, $q(t_0)$ is the amount of adsorbed material at $t=t_0$, and the other quantities were defined earlier.

The t_0 defined here is not the same quantity as the t_0 defined in Eq. 4; t_0 in Eq. 4 is equal to $(1/B)$ in Eq. 6. In Eq. 4 the starting t and starting q were both 0. In Eq. 6, $q(t_0)$ may also depend on temperature. This reversible temperature dependence is not time dependent and is the temperature coefficient of q at $t=t_0$.

Eq. 6 can be expressed in the following simpler form by defining combinations of variables as:

$$q(t) - q(t_0) = D \ln[1 + \langle B(t - t_0) \rangle] \quad (7)$$

$$\text{where } D = \frac{kT}{E_{a1}}$$

Fig. 5 shows a schematic plot of q versus log-time according to Eq. 7.

Eq. 6 and Fig. 5 show that at times short compared to $1/B$, $q(t)-q(t_0)$ is approximately zero. At times long compared to $1/B$, $q(t)-q(t_0)$ is approximately $D \ln[B(t-t_0)]$ or $D \ln(B)$

+ $D \ln(t-t_0)$. The two parameters of interest in this aging model are D , the per decade change in q for long times, and $(1/B)$, the characteristic time at which the log-time behavior begins to appear. For the simple model described in Eq. 6,

$$BD = C e^{[-v_0]}, \quad (8)$$

$$\text{where } v_0 = E_{a0} + \frac{[E_{a1} q(t_0)]}{kT}.$$

Figure 5 - Aging Model Showing Log-Time Dependence.

Therefore, BD is activated in an Arrhenius sense, if C , E_{a0} , and E_{a1} are independent of soak temperature.

It can be inferred from experimental results on high quality 8-MHz fundamental mode quartz resonators that B is a strongly decreasing function of temperature and that D is a strongly increasing function of temperature [138]. The authors are not aware of any reports on the dependence of BD on temperature.

Aging with Two Simultaneous Log-time Mechanisms.

There are no factors in Eq. 6 that could reverse the direction of the resonator aging. Since several authors have reported measurements that show a change in the direction of aging at some particular time [6,57,87,94,139,144], either a more complicated aging model must be found or there must be more than one simple log-time aging mechanism active in such resonators. For example, Fig. 6 shows schematically how two simple logarithmic aging mechanisms acting at the

same time in a particular resonator can produce aging that changes direction at a particular time.

Figure 6 - Aging Model With Two Simple Log-time Mechanisms.

For this case the early logarithmic slope and time of the maximum positive change are mostly determined by the mechanism with the larger B . The time to zero aging has a component from both mechanisms. The long term logarithmic time slope is the sum of the log-time slopes of the two mechanisms. If the two long term slopes could be made equal (compensation), the aging would rise to a fixed value and then stop.

For some cases it may turn out that there is only a limited amount of possible aging in the particular device for one of the mechanisms. This case is not consistent with Eq. 4, and has not been reported in analyses of crystal aging.

In addition to some partly exponential time dependencies in diffusion, exponential time dependencies can arise from first order rate processes associated with adsorption-

desorption [9,68,72]. These kinds of processes can have an exponential time dependence if the activation energy does not depend on the amount of adsorption/desorption. A time dependence more complicated than exponential or logarithmic can arise if the activation energy also depends on the amount of adsorption/desorption.

In one report [68], an exponential aging model and simultaneous power law (diffusion) model fitted some isothermal data better than two different simultaneous log-time models. The significance of this result for other crystal fabrication technologies or for the majority of the filters made with the same technology is not known.

In another report [72], aging data were fitted better by log-time or by square root time (diffusion) models than by exponential time models, depending on the particular resonator being studied. In this work the log-time model was the best overall model.

Two experimental accelerated aging techniques, isothermal aging and thermal step stress aging, have been used to study the aging of crystal resonators (and the aging of other devices as well). These two techniques are discussed in the next two sections.

Isothermal Aging.

In this experimental technique each device (resonator, oscillator, etc.) is stored at only one of a set of temperatures and the frequency is measured at several times of particular interest [138,145]. Nearly all reported accelerated aging experiments have been of this type. The measurement times are selected to optimize the cost and resulting use of the data. Measurement time choices depend on many factors, such as the need for fixture calibration, the number of samples, and the type of device. For determining the parameters of a log-time model for a filter application, with large numbers of samples and the need for frequent fixture calibrations, a logarithmic spacing of measurement times is particularly efficient. For an oscillator aging study, closer spaced measurements may often be desirable, e.g., to characterize frequency jumps.

Fig. 7 shows a schematic plot of some typical isothermal aging data for a negative aging device at temperatures of T_1 and T_2 (where $T_2 > T_1$). The important information here is the general shape of the curves, the times at which the rapid changes begin, and the slopes of the rapidly changing parts.

A measurement temperature, which may be different from the soak temperature, for practical reasons, is selected to make the frequency measurement as accurate as possible. This measurement temperature is often a turnover temperature for high stability resonators, or can be room

Figure 7 - Schematic Plot of Isothermal Aging at Two Temperatures.

temperature for other types of resonators. The resonator parameters may be measured directly or the resonator frequency may be measured in a test oscillator. Both kinds of measurements may be made in a temperature-controlled chamber.

For the most accurate measurements, the frequency is corrected to a fixed temperature to reduce the effects of small unavoidable temperature variations. It is important to show that the aging caused by the thermal shocks connected with the change from the soak temperature to the measurement temperature can be neglected or removed from the data.

The time dependent data is fitted (by least squares, for example) to a particular aging law to derive statistical estimates and associated confidence limits for the values of the aging law parameters or of the aging at a particular time of interest. For the log-time law the parameters are B and D; particular times of interest could be 1 year, 5 years, 20 years, etc.

Each member of a group of resonators is assigned to a different soak temperature, preferably by statistical experiment design rules. For each resonator soak temperature experiment the data are fitted to the selected aging law as above. The aging law parameters or frequency shifts calculated at a particular time of interest and their confidence limits can then be fitted to a selected law of the temperature dependence. An Arrhenius

temperature dependence law often turns out to be a useful choice.

The temperature dependence fit gives estimates and confidence limits of device aging or aging law parameters at any temperature of interest. For this temperature dependence fit, there are three sources of variability: 1) the choice of the wrong aging model, 2) the variability of the parameter estimates from each device, and 3) the error of each of the estimates.

The results of the two fittings, i.e., over time and over temperature, can only have meaning within the applicability of the assumed aging and temperature dependence laws. Since the results are highly statistical in nature, this technique can only characterize a particular fabrication technology, with the statistical meaning of the final predictions dependent on the validity of the choice of aging model, the number of samples chosen, and the number and ranges of times and temperatures selected for the design of the experiment. Within this context, statistical aging predictions can be made for any particular member of the characterized device group.

Thermal Step Stress (Differential Thermal Analysis).

In this experimental technique each device (resonator, oscillator, etc.) is stored for a fixed time interval at a series of increasing temperatures; the frequency is measured after each temperature soak [138,145]. Fig. 8 shows a schematic plot of typical thermal step stress data for a negatively aging device. The important information here is the general shape of the curve, the temperature at which rapid change begins, and the slope of the rapidly changing part. A measurement temperature is selected to make the frequency measurement as accurate as possible. This measurement temperature is often a turnover temperature or room temperature. For the most accurate measurements, the frequency is corrected to a fixed temperature to reduce the effect of small unavoidable temperature variations on the results. It is important to show that the aging caused by the thermal shocks connected with the changes from the soak temperatures to the measurement temperature can be neglected or removed from the data. This data can be plotted versus temperature to provide a curve, the shape of which is a signature of the distribution of aging mechanisms for that particular device.

For an assumed aging model, this data can also be used to determine estimates and confidence limits for the aging law parameters. For the log-time law, Eq. 5 gives an

Figure 8 - Schematic Plot of Thermal Step Stress Aging

expression for the slope of frequency versus time as a function of temperature. After each temperature step, the change in frequency during that step is the slope for that temperature, as

$$\ln \frac{df(t)}{dt} = \ln C - \frac{E_{a0} + E_{a1}f(t)}{RT} \quad (9)$$

For example, Eq. 9 shows that the logarithm of the frequency change per unit time during each temperature step should be proportional to the reciprocal of the absolute temperature of the step; the proportionality constant is

$$\frac{E_{a0} + E_{a1}f(t)}{R},$$

where $f(t)$ can be taken as the average frequency during the temperature step. The intercept of the fitted data with the $T = \text{infinity}$ axis is the logarithm of C .

After the parameters of the aging law have been determined, Eq. 9 can be used to calculate the dependence of frequency on time at any temperature of interest. These calculations can be compared with isothermal results on similar devices.

The advantage of the thermal step stress technique over the isothermal technique is that the aging parameters for a particular device can be derived in a short time, e.g., two weeks for a 16 hour time step. When the thermal step stress results compare well with the isothermal results, the thermal step stress technique can quickly

provide useful estimates of aging parameters.

If the high temperature parts of the thermal step stress results show that extraneous high temperature aging mechanisms are present, it may be necessary to use a longer time step at lower temperatures to obtain the desired data. These extraneous high temperature mechanisms may include melting processes or phase changes for some of the materials in the device being tested. The thermal step stress results provide a useful way to quickly reveal the presence of these mechanisms so that their contribution to the device long term aging can be considered and resolved.

Other Aging Characterization Techniques.

1. Soaking the completed resonators at a specified temperature for a specified period of time sufficient to produce a small but measurable aging of the resonator. Resonators with frequencies that change too much or too little, or that change in a different direction during this temperature soak, differ from other resonators in the same production lot and should, therefore, be candidates for rejection and failure mode analysis to determine the possible causes for the differences.

2. Installing the completed resonators in test ovens at the system use temperature and carefully measuring frequency changes per unit time until the change per unit time reduces to a prescribed value. If the prescribed frequency change per unit time is not reached in a prescribed time, the resonator is a candidate for rejection. Resonators that achieve the desired frequency change per unit time too early probably should also be rejected, but this is not often done.

It is very important that all thermally accelerated aging procedures be based on a specified aging model. The procedures should be performed to provide data from which parameters of the assumed aging model can be determined. Determination of the appropriate aging models requires intuition and data other than aging data, as well as the resonator aging data. Inappropriate aging models can sometimes be identified with resonator aging data alone. Some very-low-aging resonators appear to exhibit a linear frequency change with time after some stabilization period. It may be that data on resonators with log-time aging and an extended stabilization period may appear to be linear over a particular measurement time frame, such as 5 years.

There may also be apparent resonator aging mechanisms,

i.e., drift, which exhibit linear time dependence. For example, resonator frequency changes due to continuous low level radiation from space or background sources might be linear.

Crystal resonators may have many kinds of aging mechanisms. Since the various aging mechanisms can cause both positive and negative aging, compensation among the various mechanisms is possible. This compensation may occur during the early history of the resonator and then become ineffective later; or, occasionally, it may occur years after the aging starts. For this reason great care must be taken to characterize the aging mechanisms associated with a particular resonator fabrication technology over a sufficiently wide range of temperatures and time before aging predictions can be validated or qualified. After the fabrication technology is qualified to produce low-aging resonators for the required times and temperatures of the application, subsequent production must be monitored to assure that the manufacturing process remains in qualification.

Conclusions.

1. Even though several possible aging mechanisms are well understood, the aging of resonators is still not well understood.

2. Aging performance, including variations with temperature and drive level, depends on the resonator design and fabrication technology.

3. Many processing deviations can degrade aging performance.

4. High temperature processing seems necessary (but not sufficient) for the production of low-aging resonators.

5. The SC-cut, and modern ultrahigh vacuum and high temperature fabrication techniques have resulted in resonators which achieve low-aging in a shorter period of time than the best resonators made a generation ago, however, the aging of the best modern resonators after extended periods is no better today than what was reported for the best resonators in the 1960s.

6. Accelerated aging studies are useful for process control. Using accelerated aging data for long term aging predictions is possible, but considerable work and expense are required to reduce the risk of error to acceptable confidence levels.

7. The best reproducible long term aging rates seem to be a few times 10^{-11} per day. Occasional resonators exhibit aging rates of a few times 10^{-12} per day after extended periods.

8. Environmental changes can produce frequency changes that appear to be aging. This apparent aging is now called "drift."

Although the state-of-the-art in the long term aging of low-aging resonators has been on a plateau for more than a generation, there is no reason to believe that the factors responsible for limiting the achievable long term aging are insurmountable. The definitive experiments, in which all known aging mechanisms are minimized, are yet to be performed. It is the authors' hope that the review in this paper will assist future researchers in the design of experiments that result in significant improvements in aging.

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